

AN APPROACH TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING THROUGH LITERATURE

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Abstract

The paper deals with how to develop a new language learning and teaching skills through literature. It speaks about English language teaching in Indian rural class rooms setting and its barriers. The special focus is on teaching English as a second language at various levels. Teaching any other tongue like English for the beginners begins with bilingual mode in the formal indigenous class rooms with different socio-cultural background. The usage of English language is to communicate. What to communicate is a primary question. The need of the speaker in a particular context can decide the content of the communication. The purpose of speaker is conveyed through a language. So to communicate, there should be a specific content and that content is communicated either through the language or a sign. There is no communication without content and form. The content generally may be a text. The text may get the forms like prose, poetry, story, drama, biography and a novel. It is because the formal teaching and learning is recommended with particular content which is prescribed. The prescribed content is being taught through a language. While teaching a new concept of the content in regional language is not much difficult. The difficulties arise when we teach English as second language.

The content of the text in different forms is fixed and some common techniques and methods are also suggested to follow while teaching in the English class rooms. The English language teacher is also trained with support materials and resources. With all these facilities the language teacher fails to develop English communication skills either in the class rooms or outside. The present paper tries to discover why he fails? When he fails? Is it the problem lies with the teacher or the student or the both? There may be teacher induced errors while teaching English as a second language in rural class rooms. There also may be student invited errors. It is a sincere effort to find possible solutions for English learning barriers.

The learning atmosphere must be created by the English language teacher. It depends on his self-interest. It develops naturally when he has mastery in his English communication. He gets when he is good at his content, he can get mastery of it. This content is framed as literature. When he has digested this literature and probe into it, he should also think and plan to deliver his thoughts in a simple

structure of English and express it with great interest delightfully. The expression of the teacher is to so attractive and in pleasant to follow him.

Key words: - Content, Form, Literature, Expression, Communication, Probe and Design, Indigenous class rooms. Proficiency, Fluency, Context, Conceptualization, Context, Speech, Oral tradition,

The paper entitled “**An Approach to English Language Learning and Teaching through Literature**” probes into a basic question whether the language first or the literature next or is the literature first and the language next? The answer to the question needs to understand and define the two terms *Language* and *Literature* at fore hand. **Chomsky** believed that language is innate. For, **Ferdinand de Saussure** it is social phenomenon, a structured system that be viewed synchronically and diachronically. For **Aristotle**, human language has it semantic scope. And for **Henry Sweet**, language is the expression of ideas by means of speech-sounds combined into words and words are combined into sentences.

Concept of Language:-

Language is system of conventional spoken or written symbols by means of which human beings as members of a social group and participants in its culture express themselves.

The physical and emotional experience of man is communicated either with signs or with a specific means of discourse. Communication through the symbols and signs is non-verbal communication which is known as animal communication. Whereas the communication which is done by man is something more than animal communication. The concept of human knowledge is expressed with *arbitrariness*. The combination of ‘*signifier*’ and ‘*signified*’ of arbitrary system become a mode of expression which is formulated through human organs. The mechanism of speech-organs produces some specific sounds and the modulation of sounds that becomes a voice which is produced in mouth organs of man. It is gradually considered as speech. It is also called as verbal communication. Hence, speech with verbal sounds of human being is considered as verbal communication. It is based on a set of letters (Alphabet) combination with association of ideas. Various kinds of ideas of man are organized by a particular system of written expression with some word combination. The process of verbal communication finally named as language. The principal method of human communication consists of words and symbols which are used in a structure and it becomes conventional practice and conveyed through speech, writing and gesture. Human knowledge is a language which is nothing but a concept which is signified word-element which is expressed and understood in a language.

Concept of Literature:-

Literature is a body of written works. It is any collection of written works. It is a written artistic works. The term literature is translation of the German word 'Weltliteratur' which was coined by Johann Wolfgang Goethe(1749-1832) according to Oxford Dictionary, it is piece of writing that are valued as works of art, especially novels, plays and poems.

Evolution of Language and Literature:-

Human *language* is primary and *literature* is secondary. The identification of man from the animal world is represented by the development of speech/language. Man has become an individual because he is identical with his typical mode of communication. The journey from *savage* to *civilization* is marked by a language. Language is a bridge between savage and civilized man. The unique speech mechanism of man gives unique space to man which is named as human world. It is full of verbal communication. Man has developed a spoken language and used it to bounce his ideas back and forth as he feels/thinks/ likes/ in the different contexts with his fellow beings in the community. The human language is non-instinctive and it is acquired and becomes a conventional practice in the human history. It can be acquired by his willingness and with the social conducive environment of new language which enables him to learn and express his ideas in his own way.

Literature emerges next to the language. It stands after language. It begins with oral communication which has a long history in the human world. Written communication co-existed recently. Sumerians in Mesopotamia around 3200 B.C. invented writing. Since then, the idea of writing has spread out the world and different writing systems have evolved in different part of the world. When civilized man thought of recording his oral literature and his life experience of life and inevitability of recording leads him to create/constitute scripts for speech. Literature is emerged and gets its own independent form with the scripts. The script has its own particular sings/ symbols/sounds to produce specific scripts. Thousands of languages are spoken in the world today but only some languages have their own scripts to produce literature. In India for Sanskrit, Hindi, Marathi and Guajarati have been using almost the similar scripts which are based on Devanagari Lipi. Tulu language in Karnataka so far, had no scripts of its own but now it is developing its own independent unique scripts to write and has various forms of literature like 1. TuluNighantu-UpadyayaUdupi,2. MandaraRamayana-Keshava Bhatta,3. Paniyavva-Chinnnapagowda,4. Tulu Poli- A.V. Nnada. 5.A Grammar of Tulu Language-R.J.Brigel, 6.Tulu Janapada Sahitya-Viveka Raj, 7.Tulu Epics-Sri Bhagavato

and Kaveri, 8. The Epics of Siri and Legend of Kali- Chennaya and 9. Mahabharathto-Arunabju. But language like Lambani/Lamani in Karnataka has no scripts of its own even today.

Literature is next to the language because when man has become civilized and modernized creating scripts and composing scripture for his language for the identity of culture and regions. It becomes a practice and he has created a tradition. When a language has used as writing, it is naturally followed by Reading. Whatever is written in the form of words/ sentences, man begins to spell and pronounce and use it in writing and reading. The speech leads to listen and writing leads to read and thus, language skills have developed. While writing man has to think and associate his own ideas into words and thus he has been developed writing and reading skills. The person who knows to 'read and write' he is called as literate. If not, he is considered as *illiterate*. The process of learning steps into the threshold of formal learning which is later known as schooling and he gets education and becomes educated, learned and scholar and finally he himself could write creative literature like prose, poetry, short stories, novel, biography, autobiography, scientific discoveries and the several forms of literature.

Evolution of language and literature has their own history. Language is undoubtedly emerged first in the human history and later literature is emerged and which is recorded in letters and becomes a document. There are two kinds of literature namely Oral Literature and Written Literature. Again, oral literature occupies the first place and written becomes next. Oral literature is popularly known as *folk-lore* which is in kannada called as *Janapada*. The literature which is passing through mouth to ear and mouth to mouth and person to person wherein listening representation got wider scope. The people in the past before evolution of writing, they developed oral narratives on *gramadevatha* and *local deities* could become epics and various kinds of songs were created and sing in the name of local god and goddesses and on native culture and traditions. They were artistically constructed and they were in practice and gradually known as oral tradition. Oral literature are curative chants, folk tales, creations of tales, epic poems, songs, myths, spells, legends and probes and riddles. It is purely meant for singing and speaking. For example Homer's '*Iliad* and '*Odyssey*' were passed down through oral tradition. The story of *Atlantis* is an example for oral literature in Egypt that found its way into an epic poem. It is a common knowledge in India also that primary Hindu books called *Vedas* are great example for oral tradition.

English Language Teaching (ELT) in Indian rural class-rooms:-

In Indian rural class schools English is almost recommended to teach as second language. Who actually teaches English at various levels of learning? At elementary level English is being

taught in two kinds of schools. They are private and government schools. In private schools there are again English medium and regional language (kannada) medium schools and in government school's regional language is used as a medium of instruction. At elementary level in government schools Karnataka a general teacher who teaches basics of all subjects like science, mathematics, social science and languages. He is supposed to teach all but not very effectively for he is a master in one subject or the other but not in all at once naturally. A graduate teacher can be good at his subjects combination but not with all. However, he can do his classroom transaction better than the former. But the problem arises when he begins to teach English for he may not be master of English content and in English communication. He can just read and understand English prescribed text in his own way and with the support of study materials and bilingual dictionary he can play his role at his best to convey the syllabus to the students not the subject. He/she can act as a translator in bilingual method. Thereby he may be used as grammar- translation- method in the class room and write the summary of the day's class. He is not honestly happy in the English class rooms and the students too naturally. Because he himself is not exposed to the other tongue English communication and influenced by English language. Hence he is helpless to give the justice to the English class. Students in the course of learning are not free from fear of English and mechanically just following the English teacher and struggle to learn something in the class room. This is the case with the elementary level government schools.

Developing Proficiency and Fluency in English:-

At the secondary level and under graduation level, subject teachers/lecturer/assistant professors are appointed and somehow they are good at subject. The English teachers most probably are first generation learners of English and they basically passed through kannada medium in Karnataka. No doubt he is better than elementary teacher in the content of the subject with his higher studies and qualifications and also because he got training. However, he also fails to give justice in the English class rooms. Because, he is only exposed to the content-based English teaching atmosphere at his higher learning and henceforth he is unable to teach English well. But he tries to teach the content of English. And therefore he cannot expose his learners into English atmosphere. Because he has got master of English degree and qualified with certificates. Obviously he is master of English content but not of English form. For all these causes and background students even at higher level cannot get rid of fear of English. The teacher is honest and best at has *proficiency* of English content by having English knowledge.

Mere English knowledge is not sufficient to influence his students and make them to learn English naturally as in mother tongue.

The same students can be good at English communication when the teacher is good at his English *fluency*. Mere fluency of a teacher helps him to communicate but he needs sufficient content. Therefore the proficiency and fluency in English should go hand in hand because they are interdependent and complimentary to each other. The English teacher at any level should have both while teaching a unique language like English in our indigenous class rooms.

The process of conceptualization of content:-

While teaching the content, the English teacher just gives the summary of the poem or prose of any kind. But the teacher cannot conceptualize the knowledge of content in to English. Unless he creates the concept of the content, he fails to develop basic linguistic skills naturally. As he thinks and develops the concepts of the content in his mother tongue, he cannot do the same in English. Because the teacher himself is having L2 English background based. Does L2 English teacher teach L1 English? It seems to a fundamental question at one hand. Of course, he can. Teaching English in English naturally needs extra conscious effort especially for non-native speakers.

Language which is taught and learnt in the class room should be in usage both inside and outside class room. It is followed by speaking, writing and reading, and then only the teacher and the students go together in the English classroom and keep the English communication.

Contextualization of English language teaching:-

Context plays a significant role especially in English class rooms. Because teaching the English content without context, cannot create relevant concept of teaching content. Without concept the transacted content is not in one's memory and leads to insufficient learning content. Because the learner should feel something and in a way the process of learning should create a perception of the content and express. Self-expression is possible when one understands any content contextually with relevant illustrations which are directly related to learner's day to day living experience. Then, he can think his native content naturally both in mother tongue and other tongue by associating his ideas into both the intermediate languages. Contextualized content in teaching obviously draws the attention of the students and involve him with simple English application in own usage. It is to be conventional practice of the teacher and the student. Situational presentation with structural practice becomes more fruitful. Language items are presented on the situations in the class room to ensure that their meaning is clear and then practiced as formal structure by means of exercises of sufficient variety to sustain the interest

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of the learner in sufficient numbers to establish the structure in the learner's memory. The principal aim is to promote knowledge of the language system to develop the learner's competence (to use Chomsky's terms) by means of controlled performance. The assumption behind this approach seems to be that learning a language is a matter of associating the formal elements of the language system with their physical realization either as sounds in the air or as marks on paper. Essentially what is taught by this approach is the ability to compose correct sentences.

The difficulty is that the ability to compose sentences is not only ability we need to communicate. Communication only takes place when we make use of sentences to perform a variety of different acts of an essentially social nature. Thus we do not communicate just by composing sentences but we must be able to guide them properly express themselves. The basic sentence in a given language has to be looked upon as the linguistic representation of a basic pattern in the thinking of the native users of that language.

Nature of Content and Form in usage of English Language:-

Content is cognitive that can be conceptualized contextually with simple living examples and the teacher should be a facilitator as a English language teacher not just as subject teacher. To be a facilitator, he can naturally create English atmosphere with his desirable motivation and let him free mentally without fear of English and encourage him/her to react to the teacher.

Form is idealized content. If the teacher and the student are emotionally free and strong, then they can be creative and express themselves as they express in their own language. Therefore the L2 English teacher must be more emotional which enables him to conceptualize the content in the context. Natural English communication can influence the learner to involve in learning to speak English. So, the content and the form should go hand in hand. Because they are interdependent, contribute and complimentary to each other in the process of teaching and learning English. English language teacher should be good at both form and content that helps him create concepts of the content in the suitable context.

Mere giving English knowledge is not English teaching, it is simply teaching of language content not communication. The very purpose behind teaching is to communicate and it is always interpersonal in nature.

ELT interprets and encourages language teaching but not focus on English teaching in English. No language is taught but it is learnt in communicable atmosphere in natural imitation. So, the primary task of English teacher is to be good at English communication blending with fluency and proficiency and form and content.

The content is generally framed in the formal learning as a text. The text is in the form of story poetry, novel, biography, autobiography and scientific discoveries and inventions. The text book framing committee is popularly known as Board of Studies. B.O.S. of any disciplines frames the syllabus with subject related content and it is analyzed, discussed and reviewed with innovative teaching methods and techniques and skills. They are guided and recommended to follow them while teaching in the class rooms. Sometimes teachers are being trained and provided them teaching materials as a source to prepare him / her to practice in the class rooms. With all these pre-accommodated stuff, the English teacher goes to class room for many years but he is not happy. On the other hand, rising common regular complaint against learners and system. Challenges are habitually listed everywhere and discussing the same without finding out possible solutions to overcome his/ her living English class room challenges and gaps.

As English is a foreign language, naturally first generation of English speaker/ English teacher obviously find and face challenges and those innovative challenges lead him to learn new learning abilities and skills. Problems cannot be solved but challenges can be found solutions. Because, there is a constant attempt to come out of problems in the challenges, whereas there is a problem itself problem in challenges. The present paper is sincerely perusing to find some possible remedies. The English teacher makes sure of himself and herself whether he is an English teacher or English language teacher. He is between the two. Therefore he should also understand the difference between the two. He must decide where he stands in the two spaces and what role that he plays and what changes that he first undergoes and decide first whether tries to transform just English content or form. If there is a gap in him/her, he should fill the gap and play the role of a facilitator and develop some qualities of it and practice. He should accommodate himself/herself in the English class rooms by creating English language communicating atmosphere naturally by motivating the learning minds with innovative simple inter actions and reward the learners for any kind of reaction or expression and encourage them with judicious outcome. By creating a free learning English atmosphere he can achieve the end of the English teaching and break the barriers and fill the gaps in the class room communication with immediate intimate interaction with the students. It is not easy for Indian teacher of English to understand enjoy teaching literature in English. However simple it may films, color slides, music, broadcasts and introductory sketches may be used to introduce students do an alien culture. Too many explanations will kill the interest of the students. If it is a poem or a shot play, an intelligent sensitive reading by the teacher will do a world of good to the learners.

The present paper 'An Approach to English Learning and Teaching Language through Literature' tries to justify that teaching and learning English language through literature is recommended but not accommodated completely. The literature is given to the teacher and he tries to give the knowledge of literature in different forms but obviously he is not teaching English literature but he is teaching about the language. Therefore both the teacher and the students could be good at proficiency and fluency. Developing fluency is simply not easy through literature. But it is all possible with mastery of English communicative fluency and proficiency of knowledge which will enable him to become a good facilitator with his desirable communication. Ultimately it is an art of teacher and professional ethics at any level English teaching is significant not just accumulating content may not be effective and useful.

Conclusion;-

From the above discussion, it might be clear to you that literature and language are neither same nor contradictory in nature; rather literature is highly dependent on language.

Literature is an aesthetic subject which deals with the study of work and styles of various authors and writers. On the contrary, language is the only way of communication, no matter, if it is interpersonal or intrapersonal. The whole literature is based on the language in which it is written.

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